

PanoTherm: Panoramic Thermal Imaging for Object Detection and Tracking

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Abstract: Visible-light cameras are used traditionally in object detection and tracking. Thermal imaging can equally be used for this purpose, however at the cost of additional calibration efforts, expenses, and limitations concerning the field of view. Still, thermal imaging is advantageous in various scenarios and basically the only plausible technology to apply in harsh outdoor environments, in which the use of standard RGB cameras is prohibitive due to low-light conditions or in complete darkness. While panoramic imaging using visible light cameras is becoming more popular for advanced photography or action recording, limited work has been done on developing panoramic thermal cameras. In this work, we present the first panoramic thermal camera targeting the constant 360° monitoring of the environment. We describe the calibration and stitching process in detail and demonstrate how to use the camera in a vehicular scenario. Finally, we give an example of the detection and tracking of objects and discuss the advantages and disadvantages of thermal imaging for this purpose.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years visible-light cameras have become the state-of-the-art in detecting and tracking humans and objects. Following a vast amount of development in the area of Computer Vision and through the hype around autonomous driving, visible-light cameras are nowadays the standard to apply in vehicles to increase safety in road traffic. However, digital aids still lack reliability, particularly under adverse environmental conditions, leading to thousands of, partially fatal, accidents per year.

Additional mirrors on trucks or other heavy machinery, blind spot notifiers on side mirrors, and specified driver training have not led to the hoped decrease in accidents. Studies reveal alarming numbers for, *e.g.*, Germany (Luis Technology, 2023), while more recent numbers for Austria indicate no significant improvements concerning blind spot accidents in recent years (Spitzer, 2023):

- 37 thousand accidents a year with 47 thousand people involved,
- on average one hundred accidents a day, involving 128 people on average.

While these numbers are arguably high, they only concern regular traffic accidents and exclude other similar accidents with heavy machinery like, reach stackers, snow groomers, equipment on construction sites, and others.

More visibility, like bright colors (*i.e.*, a warning vest), mirrors, or visible-light cameras seem to improve this situation, but their usefulness is strongly related to the environmental conditions. Fog, rain, darkness, snow, dust, and sand will drastically reduce the ability to quickly identify human beings in or close to a blind spot.

In this work, we present a novel take on this category of problems using a low-cost panoramic thermal camera, **PanoTherm**, to remove blind spots to the greatest extent possible. Using a uniform and calibrated view, we can easily detect and track objects with certain heat signatures, especially humans. The application of our proposed development ranges from disaster scenarios, *e.g.*, identifying fire hazards and finding humans (conscious and unconscious), to the application in areas with bad visibility, *e.g.*, smoky buildings or off-road, low-light navigation. Mounted on the roof of a vehicle, persons in typical blind spot areas are immediately recognized. Furthermore, it is equally suited for surveillance situations like trespassing or maintenance tasks like pipe inspection. In a more futuristic use case, our panoramic thermal im-

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age can also be used within virtual reality (VR) applications, *e.g.*, being overlaid with a color image of a traditional panoramic camera.

Thermal and panoramic imaging have been extensively, yet separately studied. With PanoTherm, we close the gap between these fields and introduce a panoramic thermal camera, assembled with low-cost longwave infrared thermal sensors. Compared to existing, very expensive panoramic thermal hardware with a rotating sensor, the major advantage of PanoTherm is the *uninterrupted* omnidirectional view at comparably high frame rates, coming at a price tag in the low 5-digit USD area. The proposed algorithms are largely independent of the underlying hardware and can therefore be seamlessly applied to a wide range of devices. Our main contributions are:

- a thermal image calibration workflow that allows the calibration of multiple rigidly assembled thermal sensors with very little preparation;
- a working prototype for an omnidirectional thermal camera. This includes the 3D printed and assembled camera case as well as the software framework for stitching the thermal images in real-time without the need for re-calibration;
- a methodology to register the panoramic thermal camera rig with respect to its environment, giving measurements a context in the 3D world; and
- an example of object detection and tracking in the 360° thermal domain in a vehicular setup.

Finally, we demonstrate our contributions in the field and track targets not only across the individual camera views but also estimate the real-world position, visualize it in a radar-like manner, and discuss our findings in the latter of this work.

2 RELATED WORK

In the following, we quickly review the areas of camera calibration, panoramic imaging, and thermal object detection and tracking.

2.1 Camera Calibration

Intrinsically and extrinsically calibrated cameras are the foundation of any image-based real-world related measurements. Being a well-studied field, almost every camera model features its own methodology. Modern takes on single and multi-camera array calibration were presented by Zhang *et al.*, (Zhang, 2000). The foundation of all algorithms is to establish correspondences between real-world patterns

Figure 1: Exemplary thermal imagery taken with one of PanoTherm off-the-shelf thermal seek cameras.

(*e.g.*, checkerboard) and their imagery. By reducing the measured error, the camera parameters can be estimated. In the thermal domain, geometric features blocking infrared (IR) light have to be exploited to derive such correspondences (Lagüela *et al.*, 2011; Yang *et al.*, 2011; Ellmauthaler *et al.*, 2013). Wired metal structures in combination with resistors (Ng and Du, 2005), patterns printed from aluminum (Usamentiaga *et al.*, 2017), heated (Saponaro *et al.*, 2015), or cooled (Herrmann *et al.*, 2019) structures, lead to acceptable results for thermal cameras. However, with PanoTherm we implement a circular cutout board for the calibration of all cameras, described in Section 3.1.

2.2 Thermal Imagery Applications

Thermal cameras are a commonly used alternative to visible-light cameras due to their independence from visible light sources and their capacity to sense through obstructions such as fog or smoke. Gade and Moeslund (Gade and Moeslund, 2014) demonstrate advantages in complex environmental scenarios. Furthermore, thermal imaging technology has led to the development of smaller and more affordable thermal cameras (Systems, 2011), expanding their usability and impact across different sectors such as industry, medical, or home automation. Such devices utilize uncooled microbolometer sensors to capture long-wave infrared (LWIR) emissions.

Microbolometers contain vanadium oxide or amorphous silicon resistors, which change their electrical resistance depending on the impact of the electromagnetic radiance of certain wavelengths.

More specifically, LWIR sensors can capture infrared radiations with wavelengths between 8 – 14 μm . Jewett and Serway (Jewett and Serway, 2008) mention that, according to Wiens law, the emitted electromagnetic radiance of room temperature (20°) objects peaks at roughly 9 μm . Applications reach from agronomy (Yanmaz *et al.*, 2007; Halachmi *et al.*, 2019), agriculture (Vadivambal and Jayas, 2011; Messina and Modica, 2020), mainte-

Figure 2: Assembly of the panoramic thermal camera in a rectangular shape. Each camera has about 105° horizontal FOV, leaving an overlapping area between the individual cameras of approximately 15° .

nance (Hoegner and Stilla, 2009; Venegas et al., 2022), medical diagnostics (Ring and Ammer, 2012; Sousa et al., 2017), robotics (Fehlman and Hinder, 2009), surveillance (Krišto et al., 2020), to autonomous driving (Rosique et al., 2019).

2.3 Panoramic Imaging

The process of combining images into mosaics is a long-standing computer vision problem, elaborated by Milgram (Milgram, 1975) and others. Due to the advantages of panoramic images, *i.e.*, the increased field-of-view (FOV) and higher resolutions, or the same frame of reference – the applications are manifold. These include the creation of panoramic scenes for augmented reality (AR) (Wagner et al., 2010), scene understanding in the autonomous driving domain (Zhang et al., 2021), depth estimation (Zioulis et al., 2018), visual odometry (Zhang et al., 2016), or other robotics applications (Cheng et al., 2019). This versatility is also reflected in underlying camera systems. Besides the utilization of smartphones to take scenic photos, panoramic or 360° images can be captured by vastly different sensors setups, *e.g.*, rigid multi-camera arrays (Lin et al., 2018), fast rotating single cameras (Thomas et al., 2019), fish-eye lenses (Ho and Budagavi, 2017), or the usage of panoramic annular lenses (Powell, 1994).

In the context of thermal imaging, sensor setups resort to rotating single cameras (Thomas et al., 2019), the application of a catadioptric mirror (Zeng et al., 2020), or, similar to our approach, a multi-camera setup (Cowan et al., 2019).

However, all approaches rely on either knowing rigid transformations between individual cameras or the pan-tilt-yaw state of acquired images. Such information is leveraged to obtain a single panorama.

2.4 Thermal Object Detection

Numerous (semi-) autonomous applications like collision avoidance, obstacle detection, pedestrian detec-

tion, and more, benefit from object detection and object tracking. Since this is a well-researched area, we will only highlight a view of relevant works within the thermal domain. With the success of deep learning-based object detection, single-stage object detection methods such as you only look once (YOLO) (Redmon et al., 2016) or single shot detector (SSD) (Liu et al., 2016) were applied in the thermal domain. Namely, Krivsto *et al.*, (Krišto et al., 2020) employ YOLO-based methods, and Dai *et al.*, (Dai et al., 2021) implement a method based on the SSD architecture. This method called *TIRNet*, modifies the original SSD model architecture by extending it with residual branches, to extract features from the low-resolution IR images.

The tracking-by-detection (TBD) paradigm successfully dominates various multi-object tracking benchmarks, such as MOT17 (Milan et al., 2016) or MOT20 (Dendorfer et al., 2020). TBD methods, *e.g.*, simple online and realtime (SORT) (Bewley et al., 2016)-based trackers or ByteTrack (Zhang et al., 2022) associate bounding boxes resulting from the object detection method to create tracks. In Section 6, we demonstrate the use of YOLO and ByteTrack with PanoTherm to precisely detect, track, and localize humans for accident avoidance.

3 MULTI CAMERA ARRAY

Traditional thermal cameras for small-scale monitoring feature a very limited horizontal field-of-view (FOV) of 15° to 60° . The PanoTherm assembly requires FOVs of at least 105° with four cameras. One capable and cost-efficient candidate is the Thermal Seek Mosaic Cores C312NPX⁴ featuring a 2.2mm lens and 320×240 pixels at a frame rate of about 27Hz. The horizontal FOVs measure 105° , yielding a 15° degree overlap between the views. In Figure 1 we showcase an exemplary image taken with one of the

⁴Mosaic Core: <https://www.thermal.com/mosaic-core-320x240-2mm.html>

utilized thermal cameras. Figure 2 depicts the custom 3D printed enclosure, the rectangular arrangement of the cameras, and their approximate FOV projections.

Each camera is connected to a USB3-Hub based on the assembly, such that only a single power and a single data cable connect the device to a computing platform (*e.g.*, laptop computer, single board computer). Figure 4 depicts a panoramic image captured with PanoTherm consisting of the four individual cameras. Due to the comparably low amount of data (*i.e.*, only a fraction of modern color images) a serial USB connection is more than sufficient to capture images simultaneously.

3.1 Camera Calibration

Because of their shared characteristics and comparable lens geometry, the pinhole camera model (Hartley and Zisserman, 2003) can be applied to commonly used thermal cameras. Thus, allowing us to apply the same geometric and mathematical properties to compute intrinsic properties. Points in images $\mathbf{x}_I \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and the 3D points in the world $\mathbf{x}_W \in \mathbb{R}^4$ are expressed as homogeneous coordinates, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{x}_I = (x_i, y_i, 1)^\top$ and $\mathbf{x}_W = (x_w, y_w, z_w, 1)^\top$. Following the pinhole camera model, the relation between image and world points is formalized by the camera projection matrix $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 4}$ as follows

$$\mu \mathbf{x}_I = \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x}_W \quad \text{with } \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{K} [\mathbf{R} \mid \mathbf{t}]. \quad (1)$$

Here, μ corresponds to an arbitrary scale factor. The projection matrix \mathbf{P} is composed of the extrinsic parameters rotation $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and translation vector $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ as well as the intrinsic parameters, *i.e.*, the camera matrix $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$. Camera calibration with a planar calibration pattern uses this relation, by assuming the z coordinate of 3D world points to be 0. Expressing this assumption with Equation (1) yields

$$\mu \mathbf{x}_I = \mathbf{K} \begin{bmatrix} r_{00} & r_{01} & r_{02} & t_0 \\ r_{10} & r_{11} & r_{12} & t_1 \\ r_{20} & r_{21} & r_{22} & t_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_w \\ y_w \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{H} \begin{bmatrix} x_w \\ y_w \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ corresponds to the homography, which relates the real-world calibration points with the detected positions in pixel space. Since \mathbf{H} is defined up to a scale factor, at least 4 *point-to-point* correspondences are necessary to obtain a solution.

Real cameras deviate from the optimal pinhole camera model due to imperfections introduced by their lenses, *i.e.*, the pinhole aperture, as well as \mathbf{x}_W and \mathbf{x}_I , being not co-linear. Hence, the mathematical model has to account for lens distortion. Following (Hartley and Zisserman, 2003; Heikkila and

Figure 3: (Left) The common image calibration approach utilizing an asymmetric grid in front of an LCD screen. (Right) Thermal profile of the asymmetric circular calibration pattern in front of an LCD.

Silvén, 1997), radial and tangential distortion can be approximately corrected by

$$\mathbf{x}_c = \mathbf{x}_d + \mathcal{F}_D(\mathbf{x}_d, \delta), \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{x}_d \in \mathbb{R}^2$ being the distorted image pixel, $\mathbf{x}_c \in \mathbb{R}^2$ being the corrected image pixel and \mathcal{F}_D being a higher order polynomial with coefficients

$$\delta = (k_1, k_2, \dots, p_1, p_2, \dots)^\top. \quad (4)$$

Given n images with m calibration points each, Zhang (Zhang, 2000) proposed to apply the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (Moré, 1977) for the maximum-likelihood estimation (MLE), *i.e.*,

$$\sum_i^n \sum_j^m \|\mathbf{x}_{ij} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{K}, \delta, \mathbf{R}_i, \mathbf{t}_i, \mathbf{x}_{W,j})\|^2. \quad (5)$$

3.2 Pattern Calibration

Pattern-based calibration approaches have successfully been shown by Vidas *et al.*, (Vidas et al., 2012), being a direct inspiration to our approach. We utilize an **asymmetric circular calibration pattern**. To detect the pattern in the thermal image, the IR light is blocked by simple irregular circular cut-outs. The resulting plate is placed in front of the liquid-crystal display (LCD) to block off light around the irregular circles. Figure 3 (left) shows the detected pattern and Figure 3 (right) the thermal response, where the peaks are the passed-through IR radiation of the monitor.

Backlights used in modern computer screens are significantly warmer than the ambient room temperature. Hence, the temperature difference between the calibration board in front and the screen itself is visible in the thermal image, consequently allowing us to apply traditional calibration methods. Commonly used tools like the *OpenCV* (Bradski, 2000) can be directly applied to the calibration process.

Implementation Details The pattern is detected using *OpenCV*'s `findCirclesGrid` function. However, if the blob detection algorithm is not successful,

we simply apply the `adaptiveThreshold` function. Passing the resulting image to `findCirclesGrid` usually succeeds in extracting the calibration pattern from the thermal image. Hence, we can make use of the `calibrateCamera` function to retrieve a calibration.

3.3 Image acquisition

Acquiring images in a fixed multi-camera arrangement poses specific challenges that do not require addressing within a single-camera panoramic pipeline, *e.g.*, synchronization of the utilized camera heads or bandwidth considerations. Especially in the context of panoramic images that capture moving objects, synchronization is highly important to avoid ghosting and other artifacts.

PanoTherm relies on event-driven camera call-backs and polling to achieve synchronization. Since each camera supports frame rates of up to 27 Hz, a registered call-back function for each camera head updates the separate data structures once a frame is ready in an asynchronous manner. To create a panorama, the data structures are naively polled and processed as depicted in Figure 6. On modern computer hardware, the cost of storage and processing of a panorama sequence is negligible. Hence, in our experiments, the synchronicity of the acquired frames proved to be sufficient as we did not witness artifacts between frames for moving objects.

4 IMAGE STITCHING

Image stitching is a fundamental computer vision task that involves combining multiple overlapping images to create a panoramic scene. The number of different algorithms and approaches showcase the long-standing research interest in this problem (Szeliski et al., 2007).

In many image stitching workflows, *e.g.*, the case of panoramic imaging from a single camera (Wagner et al., 2010), the camera positions are unknown and therefore feature tracking and matching, as well as global image alignment, is necessary to produce a panoramic image. This is different in a rigid camera setup. Once calibrated, the panoramic image can be composed by simply utilizing the previously derived camera matrices.

4.1 Stereo Calibration

To find the extrinsic parameters between cameras, feature matching is usually employed (Hartley and

Zisserman, 2003). However, in cases with narrow, distorted, or low-resolution overlapping regions, feature-extraction methods such as SIFT (Lowe, 1999) and ORB (Rublee et al., 2011), are not insufficient to extract congruent features. Therefore, we utilize easily detectable patterns, *i.e.*, the calibration pattern depicted in Figure 3, and place them in the overlapping FOV of adjacent cameras to find correspondences. With this, standard stereo calibration can be applied to estimate the rotation and translation between the cameras.

Given a point in image i $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_i, y_i, 1)^\top$ and in the same pixel coordinates which correspond to the point \mathbf{x}_i in image j $\mathbf{x}_j = (x_j, y_j, 1)^\top$, the relation

$$\mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{F} \mathbf{x}_j = 0 \quad (6)$$

is leveraged to calculate the extrinsic parameters. $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ corresponds to the fundamental matrix which encapsulates the algebraic representation of the epipolar geometry of the scene. We refer the reader to Hartley and Zisserman (Hartley and Zisserman, 2003) for more details.

4.2 Cylindrical Warping

The obtained extrinsics are utilized in cylindrical image warping. We chose to warp and blend our obtained scenes, due to its advantages for visualization and registration. This includes the possibility to easily unwrap the map on a planar surface and utilize the geometric properties for our registration purposes.

To warp the images on the cylindrical canvas, we apply backward mapping. Following (Wagner et al., 2010), we apply

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{O} \cdot \mu(\mathbf{x}_{\text{cyl}}) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{camera}} = \mathbf{K} \cdot \delta(\pi(\mathbf{R})) \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{pixel}} = \text{interpolate}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{camera}}) \quad (9)$$

to project points on the cylinder \mathbf{x}_{cyl} into the pixel coordinates $\mathbf{x}_{\text{pixel}}$. First, we apply the function μ to project the point on the cylinder to a ray. This ray is then rotated according to an orientation \mathbf{O} . With the function π , we convert \mathbf{R} into the image plane. After applying radial distortion with δ , we can project the point into the camera frame by multiplying it with the intrinsic matrix \mathbf{K} . Finally, the pixel value is chosen by interpolation. This yields $\mathbf{x}_{\text{pixel}}$, the color value for the panoramic coordinate \mathbf{x}_{cyl} .

4.3 Limitations

The number of cameras we employ is minimal concerning our goal to capture a full 360° panorama. While Figure 4 shows good geometric accuracy,

Figure 4: A naively stitched panorama (top) in comparison with a calibrated stitched panorama (bottom) of the same scene. The improvements are visible in the overlapping regions, *e.g.*, there are no duplicate persons in the center of the panorama and the structure of objects is consistent across cameras.

Figure 5: Illustration of the image to 3D world point mapping through the cylindrical coordinate system. Image coordinates x_i, y_i are mapped into cylindrical coordinates α_i, β_i . Knowing the 3D positions of the marker corners, *i.e.*, x_w, y_w, z_w , we can solve the PnP problem and resolve the transformation between C_c and C_w .

seams in the overlap areas are visible. Our use case targets the detection of thermal signatures, which means that the real temperature values, respectively the visual appeal of the panorama, are less important. Each camera is automatically adapting to spread the available value range, *i.e.*, $[0, 255]$, to maximize the preserved information content. This implies that the individual ranges correspond to different absolute temperature ranges, resulting in a panoramic view similar to one created from multiple RGB cameras missing brightness and contrast adaption.

As PanoTherm is constructed out of separate cameras, the parallax between frames is apparent. These limitations could be addressed with geometrical algorithms, *e.g.*, multi-perspective plane sweep (MPPS) algorithm (Kang et al., 2004; Uyttendaele et al., 2004) or image based solutions, *e.g.*, Stretching Stereo (Kang et al., 2004).

5 CAMERA-TO-WORLD REGISTRATION

In order to give measurements in the panoramic view meaning in terms of direction and distance with regards to the given environment, the camera rig has to be registered in a coordinate system. We employ a modified version of the known Perspective-3-Point (P3P) algorithm (Fischler and Bolles, 1981) used for panorama localization in Arth *et al.*, (Arth et al., 2011).

PanoTherm is placed in a given environment with one of the cameras facing to the front to reduce the impact of image distortion. In the field of view of this camera, a flat AR toolkit (ARTK+) marker (Wagner and Schmalstieg, 2007) is placed to form the world coordinate center C_w . As our panoramic image is a mapping onto a cylindrical surface each pixel in the panorama can be represented as a ray emanating from the center of the cylinder through the cylindrical surface with two angles, α and β . More specifically, a point in the panoramic image domain $\mathbf{x}_{\text{pano}} = (x_{\text{pano}}, y_{\text{pano}})$ is converted into cylindrical coordinates $\mathbf{x}_{\text{cyl}} = (x_{\text{cyl}}, y_{\text{cyl}})$ as follows

$$x_{\text{cyl}} = s\alpha = s \tan^{-1} \frac{x_{\text{pano}}}{f}, \quad (10)$$

$$y_{\text{cyl}} = s\beta = s \frac{y_{\text{pano}}}{\sqrt{x_{\text{pano}}^2 + f^2}}. \quad (11)$$

Here, s is a scaling factor and f corresponds to the focal length (Szeliski et al., 2007).

We can thereby convert image measurements to rays emanating from the center of C_c and going through individual points \mathbf{x}_{cyl} , and mea-

Figure 6: Block diagram representation of the proposed concept around PanoTherm. The images acquired by individual sensors (top left) are registered and stitched into a panoramic view (top middle). Similarly, MOT is used to detect humans in the actual imagery (top right). Using the detection results, the registration, and the cylindrical representation, we can represent the position and motion of detected objects with respect to the vehicle registered (bottom).

sure their pairwise angle. The corresponding 3D points of the marker corners all have coordinates $(\pm l_{artk}/2, \pm l_{artk}/2, h_{artk})$. In a general setup, we assume $h_{artk} = 0$ which results in the marker center being the center of the world coordinate system C_w .

Figure 5 depicts an illustration of these relationships. Reformulating the P3P problem we solve the polynomial equation system similar to the one solved in the pinhole case, giving us the transformation between the coordinate systems C_c and C_w in the form of $[\mathbf{R}_{pt} | \mathbf{t}_{pt}]$.

5.1 Real World Position Estimator

For the composition of the panoramic image, we utilize backward warping (see Section 4.2). To project a point from the panoramic image into the real world, we apply forward warping.

In a practical scenario, we can assume that the observed environment is mostly flat and can be approximated through a ground plane P . Putting the ARTK+ marker upright on the ground during registration, P is trivially given as $z = 0$. First, we can convert \mathbf{x}_{cyl} following Equations (10) and (11). Then, we convert it into a ray emanating the coordinate center C_c and going through \mathbf{x}_{cyl} . Note that the 3D world coordinates of the center of C_c are given by

$$\mathbf{c}_c = -\mathbf{R}_{pt}^T \mathbf{t}_{pt}. \quad (12)$$

Lastly, we intersect this ray with the plane P to determine the approximate 3D position, *i.e.*, the distance and heading, relative to the world coordinate system C_w .

An illustration of this concept is later shown in our experimental setup in Figure 10. The relative heading α' determines the relative orientation of an object to C_w , respectively the distance d can be calculated from β'_1 . From the assumption that the object in question is oriented upwards, we can additionally use β'_2 to determine the approximate object height.

6 EXPERIMENTS

To evaluate PanoTherm, we employ the sensor system on a real car. This includes the registration of our system with respect to the car itself, the detection and tracking of pedestrians in proximity to the car in the panoramic image, and the utilization of the cylindrical geometry to re-project the detected objects concerning the car into real-world coordinates. Figure 6 displays the workflow of our use case.

6.1 Registration

As we are mainly interested in blind-spot avoidance on a vehicle, we perform an illustrative setup as shown in Figure 7 and leave out exact measurements for now. PanoTherm is mounted on the roof of a vehicle with one of the cameras facing to the front. A flat ARTK+ marker (Wagner and Schmalstieg, 2007) made from steel with a known edge length l_{artk} is mounted on the engine hood pointing upwards. For simplicity, we measure the approximate height above ground h_{artk} . Similarly, we measure the approximate distance of the marker from the front end of the car,

Figure 7: Registration with respect to a given environment. As the camera rig is internally calibrated and represents the coordinate center C_c , it is sufficient to use a standard ARTK+ marker with a known size on the engine hood with a known approximate height above ground.

v_{artk} , with a standard meter. Mounting the marker in the middle of the hood, we can further infer the distance of the marker center to $w/2$ with w denoting the known width of the car.

Once the engine of the car warms up, the marker becomes visible in the image of the front-facing camera, allowing us to detect it in the thermal image⁵. An example image is shown in Figure 8. By using h_{artk} for the z -coordinate of the marker corners in the registration step described in Section 5, we can place the world coordinate center C_w perpendicularly below the marker center on the ground plane P , such that our assumption of P given by $z = 0$ holds. We finally arrive at a registration of PanoTherm with respect to C_w , being a coordinate system anchored to the vehicle.

6.2 Object Detection and Tracking

We utilize a YOLOv8 model and train it on the KAIST (Hwang et al., 2015) dataset before applying fine-tuning on a small custom dataset. As described previously, the thermal range between single cameras is not equalized over the whole panorama to improve the visible range of each image. Therefore, we abstain from using image-based re-identification models and leverage motion-based predictions in the multi-object tracking (MOT) module. Note that our main goal is to prove the proposed concept and not the evaluation of different detection and tracking methods in terms of performance in the thermal domain. An example of

⁵Note that we used manual thresholding for simplicity, however, a targeted implementation of ARTK+ could detect the marker automatically as well.

Figure 8: Thermal signature of the marker as seen from the front-facing camera.

human detection using this setup is shown in the red frame in Figure 9.

6.3 Reprojection and Height Estimation

The MOT framework leaves us with bounding boxes $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^6$, each defined by identifier, class, height, width, and location in the image domain. To project the lower edge of the bounding box into real-world 3D coordinates, we utilize the geometrical properties of the cylindrical projection (see Section 5.1). The position of the bounding box in 3D is further processed to obtain the height of the detected object. For this, we again intersect the vertical plane of the detection with the ray resulting from the upper edge of the bounding box. Since PanoTherm is fully registered, the conversion between 3D world coordinate system C_w and cylindrical coordinate system C_c is solved. Hence, we can simply apply $[\mathbf{R}_{pt} | \mathbf{t}_{pt}]$ to convert the coordinates from one frame into another.

Figure 10 showcases the geometrical relation of these two coordinate frames in our use case. This leaves us not only with the 3D position in world coordinates but also with the height of the object.

Since the viewing angle is obstructed by the car roof, we apply a manually picked threshold to the height and width of the bounding box. With this, we can guess if the feet of the pedestrian correspond with the lower edge of the detected bounding box. If this is not the case, we assume an average body height of $1.7m$. Therefore, we again are able to infer the position of the pedestrian by intersecting the ray through the upper edge of the bounding box with the bounding box plane which is perpendicular to the ground. Note, that our workflow is not restricted to the detection and tracking of pedestrians.

6.4 Discussion

During our experiments, we noticed a set of issues that need further investigation. First, the use of ap-

Figure 9: Tracking a human across several frames in the panoramic space. Left, the panorama, the center bottom point, and the raw output of the MOT are shown. Middle, the ray from the center of C_c through the panorama wrapped onto the cylindrical surface is shown. Right, the motion between individual frames with respect to C_w , respectively the vehicle is depicted.

Figure 10: Left, the top-down view to determine the heading of an object relative to the vehicle, *i.e.*, α' is depicted. Right, the side view to determine the distance d of an object through the angle β_1' is shown. If we assume an object to be upright, we can additionally use β_2' to determine the approximate height of the object as well.

proximate measurements certainly harms the accuracy of our registration method. Depending on the actual use case, mounting the marker in a different setup w.r.t. to the vehicle and adapting the assumptions about the ground plane P might be advantageous. Second, the accuracy of our setup was only empirically evaluated. However, measuring the end-to-end accuracy using different technologies, *e.g.*, laser distance meters, is required to create more trustworthy results. Third, technically the current hardware setups cannot deliver results at full frame rate. This is an inherent flaw of certain parts of our implementation and the intermediate hardware used, which can be resolved. Finally, we did neither evaluate the performance of the MOT module nor did we test PanoTherm under adverse environmental conditions yet. This is subject to a pending in-depth investigation.

7 CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduce PanoTherm, a concept to build a thermal panoramic camera from low-cost longwave infrared thermal sensors. We describe an

algorithm for simple calibration of the individual sensors into a camera rig. Similarly, we outline a method to register the camera to its environment to establish real-world measurements. Finally, we demonstrate the plausibility of this concept on detecting and tracking a person in the near environment of the vehicle.

While we demonstrate this as a proof-of-concept, several open points are subject to investigation in the future, both in the algorithmic and the technical domain. The calibration routines we use still suffer from inaccuracies related to the simplicity of the method and the very narrow field of overlap between individual cameras. Additional improvements in this domain would automatically enhance both the visual appeal of a stitched panorama, as well as - more importantly - the geometric accuracy of any subsequent calculation. In terms of the technical components we use, the real outdoor applicability of the current setup will depend on the creation of a more ruggedized housing for the sensor, together with proper mounting options on a given vehicle. Future improvements will focus on the development of further concepts in the domain of off-highway machinery, such as excavators, snow groomers or reach stackers.

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REFERENCES

- Arth, C., Klopschitz, M., Reitmayr, G., and Schmalstieg, D. (2011). Real-Time Self-Localization From Panoramic Images on Mobile Devices. In *Int. Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*.
- Bewley, A., Ge, Z., Ott, L., Ramos, F. T., and Upcroft, B. (2016). Simple Online and Realtime Tracking. In *Int. Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*.
- Bradski, G. (2000). The OpenCV Library. *Dr. Dobb's Journal of Software Tools*.
- Cheng, R., Wang, K., Lin, S., Hu, W., Yang, K., Huang, X., Li, H., Sun, D., and Bai, J. (2019). Panoramic Annular Localizer: Tackling the Variation Challenges of Outdoor Localization Using Panoramic Annular Images and Active Deep Descriptors. In *Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference*.
- Cowan, L. V., Babington, J., Carles, G., Perciado, M. A., Wood, A., and Harvey, A. R. (2019). 360° snapshot imaging with a convex array of long-wave infrared cameras. In *Proc. of Propagation Through and Characterization of Atmospheric and Oceanic Phenomena*.
- Dai, X., Yuan, X., and Wei, X. (2021). Tirnet: Object Detection in Thermal Infrared Images for Autonomous Driving. *Applied Intelligence*, 51:1244–1261.
- Dendorfer, P., Rezatofghi, H., Milan, A., Shi, J., Cremers, D., Reid, I., Roth, S., Schindler, K., and Leal-Taixé, L. (2020). MOT20: A Benchmark for Multi-Object Tracking in Crowded Scenes. *arXiv CoRR*, abs/2003.09003.
- Ellmauthaler, A., da Silva, E. A., Pagliari, C. L., Gois, J. N., and Neves, S. R. (2013). A Novel Iterative Calibration Approach for Thermal Infrared Cameras. In *Int. Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*.
- Fehlman, W. L. and Hinders, M. K. (2009). *Mobile Robot Navigation With Intelligent Infrared Image Interpretation*. Springer.
- Fischler, M. A. and Bolles, R. C. (1981). Random Sample Consensus: A Paradigm for Model Fitting With Applications to Image Analysis and Automated Cartography. *Communications of the ACM*, 24(6):381–395.
- Gade, R. and Moeslund, T. B. (2014). Thermal Cameras and Applications: A Survey. *Machine vision and Applications*, 25:245–262.
- Halachmi, I., Guarino, M., Bewley, J., and Pastell, M. (2019). Smart Animal Agriculture: Application of Real-Time Sensors to Improve Animal Well-Being and Production. *Annual Review of Animal Biosciences*, 7:403–425.
- Hartley, R. and Zisserman, A. (2003). *Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision*. Cambridge University Press.
- Heikkila, J. and Silvén, O. (1997). A Four-Step Camera Calibration Procedure With Implicit Image Correction. In *Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 1106–1112. IEEE.
- Herrmann, T., Migniot, C., and Aubreton, O. (2019). Thermal Camera Calibration With Cooled Down Chessboard. In *In Proc. of the Quantitative InfraRed Thermography Conference*.
- Ho, T. and Budagavi, M. (2017). Dual-Fisheye Lens Stitching for 360-Degree Imaging. In *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*.
- Hoegner, L. and Stilla, U. (2009). Thermal Leakage Detection on Building Facades Using Infrared Textures Generated by Mobile Mapping. In *Proc. of the Joint Urban Remote Sensing Event*. IEEE.
- Hwang, S., Park, J., Kim, N., Choi, Y., and Kweon, I. S. (2015). Multispectral Pedestrian Detection: Benchmark Dataset and Baselines. In *Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*.
- Jewett, J. W. and Serway, R. (2008). *Physics for Scientists and Engineers with Modern Physics*. Vectors, 7th edition.
- Kang, S. B., Szeliski, R., and Uyttendaele, M. (2004). Seamless Stitching Using Multi-Perspective Plane Sweep. Technical Report MSR-TR-2004-48, Microsoft Research.
- Krišto, M., Ivacic-Kos, M., and Pobar, M. (2020). Thermal Object Detection in Difficult Weather Conditions Using YOLO. *IEEE Access*, 8:125459–125476.
- Lagüela, S., González-Jorge, H., Armesto, J., and Arias, P. (2011). Calibration and Verification of Thermographic Cameras for Geometric Measurements. *Infrared Physics & Technology*, 54(2):92–99.
- Lin, H.-S., Chang, C.-C., Chang, H.-Y., Chuang, Y.-Y., Lin, T.-L., and Ouhyoung, M. (2018). A Low-Cost Portable Polycamera for Stereoscopic 360 Imaging. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*, 29(4):915–929.
- Liu, W., Anguelov, D., Erhan, D., Szegedy, C., Reed, S., Fu, C.-Y., and Berg, A. C. (2016). SSD: Single Shot Multibox Detector. In *Europ. Conf. on Computer Vision (ECCV)*.
- Lowe, D. G. (1999). Object Recognition From Local Scale-Invariant Features. In *Int. Conf. on Computer Vision (ICCV)*.
- Luis Technology (2023). Unfälle im toten Winkel – Studie zu Unfalltypen. <https://www.abbiegeassistenz.de/studie-zu-unfalltypen/>. Accessed Oct. 20, 2023).
- Messina, G. and Modica, G. (2020). Applications of UAV Thermal Imagery in Precision Agriculture: State of the Art and Future Research Outlook. *Remote Sensing*, 12(9):1491.
- Milan, A., Leal-Taixé, L., Reid, I., Roth, S., and Schindler, K. (2016). MOT16: A Benchmark for Multi-Object Tracking. *arXiv CoRR*, abs/1603.00831.

- Milgram, D. L. (1975). Computer Methods for Creating Photomosaics. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 100(11):1113–1119.
- Moré, J. J. (1977). The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm: implementation and theory. In *Proc. of the Conference on Numerical Analysis*, pages 105–116.
- Ng, Y.-M. H. and Du, R. (2005). Acquisition of 3D Surface Temperature Distribution of a Car Body. In *IEEE Int. Conference on Information Acquisition*, pages 16–20.
- Powell, I. (1994). Panoramic lens. *Applied Optics*, 33(31):7356–7361.
- Redmon, J., Divvala, S., Girshick, R., and Farhadi, A. (2016). You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection. In *Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*.
- Ring, E. and Ammer, K. (2012). Infrared Thermal Imaging in Medicine. *Physiolog. Measurement*, 33(3):33–46.
- Rosique, F., Navarro, P. J., Fernández, C., and Padilla, A. (2019). A Systematic Review of Perception System and Simulators for Autonomous Vehicles Research. *Sensors*, 19(3):648–677.
- Rublee, E., Rabaud, V., Konolige, K., and Bradski, G. (2011). ORB: An efficient alternative to SIFT or SURF. In *Int. Conf. on Computer Vision (ICCV)*.
- Saponaro, P., Sorensen, S., Rhein, S., and Kambhmettu, C. (2015). Improving Calibration of Thermal Stereo Cameras Using Heated Calibration Board. In *Int. Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, pages 4718–4722. IEEE.
- Sousa, E., Vardasca, R., Teixeira, S., Seixas, A., Mendes, J., and Costa-Ferreira, A. (2017). A Review on the Application of Medical Infrared Thermal Imaging in Hands. *Infrared Physics & Technology*, 85(4):315–323.
- Spitzer, P. (2023). Sehen und Gesehen werden: Unfälle im toten Winkel und aufgrund von Sichtbehinderungen – Fokusreport 2023. <https://grosse-schuetzen-kleine.at/publikationen/sehen-und-gesehen-werden-unfaelle-im-toten-winkel-und-aufgrund-von-sichtbehinderungen-fokusreport-2023>. Accessed Oct. 20, 2023).
- Systems, F. C. V. (2011). Uncooled Detectors for Thermal Imaging Cameras. http://www.flirmedia.com/MMC/CVS/Apl_Stories/AS_0015_EN.pdf.
- Szeliski, R. et al. (2007). Image alignment and stitching: A tutorial. *Foundations and Trends® in Computer Graphics and Vision*, 2(1):1–104.
- Thomas, A., Leboucher, V., Cotinat, A., Finet, P., and Gilbert, M. (2019). UAV Localization Using Panoramic Thermal Cameras. In *Conf. on Computer Vision Systems (ICVS)*, pages 754–767. Springer.
- Usamentiaga, R., Garcia, D., Ibarra-Castanedo, C., and Maldague, X. (2017). Highly Accurate Geometric Calibration for Infrared Cameras Using Inexpensive Calibration Targets. *Measurement*, 112:105–116.
- Uyttendaele, M., Criminisi, A., Kang, S., Winder, S., Szeliski, R., and Hartley, R. (2004). Image-Based Interactive Exploration of Real-World Environments. *Computer Graphics and Applications*, 24(3):52–63.
- Vadivambal, R. and Jayas, D. S. (2011). Applications of Thermal Imaging in Agriculture and Food Industry—A Review. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 4:186–199.
- Venegas, P., Ivorra, E., Ortega, M., and Sáez de Ocáriz, I. (2022). Towards the Automation of Infrared Thermography Inspections for Industrial Maintenance Applications. *Sensors*, 22(2):613.
- Vidas, S., Lakemond, R., Denman, S., Fookes, C., Sridharan, S., and Wark, T. (2012). A Mask-Based Approach for the Geometric Calibration of Thermal-Infrared Cameras. *IEEE Trans. on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 61(6):1625–1635.
- Wagner, D., Mulloni, A., Langlotz, T., and Schmalstieg, D. (2010). Real-Time Panoramic Mapping and Tracking on Mobile Phones. In Lok, B., Klinker, G., and Nakatsu, R., editors, *IEEE Conf. on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces*.
- Wagner, D. and Schmalstieg, D. (2007). ARToolKitPlus for Pose Tracking on Mobile Devices. In *Proc. 12th Computer Vision Winter Workshop (CVWW), 2007*.
- Yang, R., Yang, W., Chen, Y., and Wu, X. (2011). Geometric Calibration of IR Camera Using Trinocular Vision. *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, 29(24):3797–3803.
- Yanmaz, L. E., Okumus, Z., and Dogan, E. (2007). Instrumentation of Thermography and Its Applications in Horses. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 6(7):858–862.
- Zeng, X., Lan, J., and Gao, X. (2020). The Design of a Catadioptric Omnidirectional Thermal Imaging System Based on the Combination of Genetic Algorithm and Gradient Descent. *Optics & Laser Technology*, 122:1058–1061.
- Zhang, J., Ma, C., Yang, K., Roitberg, A., Peng, K., and Stiefelhagen, R. (2021). Transfer Beyond the Field of View: Dense Panoramic Semantic Segmentation via Unsupervised Domain Adaptation. *Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference*, 23(7):9478–9491.
- Zhang, Y., Sun, P., Jiang, Y., Yu, D., Weng, F., Yuan, Z., Luo, P., Liu, W., and Wang, X. (2022). ByteTrack: Multi-Object Tracking by Associating Every Detection Box. In *Europ. Conf. on Computer Vision (ECCV)*.
- Zhang, Z. (2000). A Flexible New Technique for Camera Calibration. *IEEE Trans. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 22(11):1330–1334.
- Zhang, Z., Rebecq, H., Forster, C., and Scaramuzza, D. (2016). Benefit of Large Field-Of-View Cameras for Visual Odometry. In *Int. Conf. on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*.
- Zioulis, N., Karakottas, A., Zarpalas, D., and Daras, P. (2018). Omnidepth: Dense Depth Estimation for Indoors Spherical Panoramas. In *Europ. Conf. on Computer Vision (ECCV)*.